

INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGIES IN ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE (EFL) TEACHING AT STATE AND PRIVATE HIGHER EDUCATION IN INDONESIA

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Abstract: The study aims at exploring instructional strategies applied by English lecturers in teaching English course in university. It focused on the ways of lecturers communicate their instructional materials to the students. This study used qualitative research method with a case study in state and private university. The data were collected by observing the classroom interaction, all interactions are put in field note and video. The research result reveals there are some instructional strategies found from the classroom. There are beginning strategies, explaining strategies, teaching-learning strategies, taking attention strategies, technological strategies, seating arrangement strategies and closing strategies. The strategies are helpful for students to interact actively in the classroom. Therefore, it can be concluded that the lecturers should be creative and innovative to explore strategies that can make their students interactive in the classroom.

INTRODUCTION

Every lecturer has own way to communicate the teaching materials in the classroom. Therefore, using appropriate strategies in the class is essential to the students' learning outcomes. As Sellnow et.al (2015) states learning outcomes by which instructional communication may be measured include affection (appreciation, perceived value, utility), cognition (knowledge, comprehension, understanding), and behaviour. Moreover, the strategies used by the lecturers should also engage students to actively participate in the classroom activities. Effective learning process occurs when both teacher and students interact and participate in learning activities. Participatory type of learning process will encourage mutual exchange of information; stimulate interests as well a recognition of respect among the teachers and students (Abdullah,et.al,2011). The students will be interested to participate in learning process if the lecturers apply effective strategies in the classroom.

In relation to the studies above, Allen (2017) states that instructional communication researchers explore how student learning strategies, instructor teaching strategies and classroom management practices, instructor and student characteristics, and initiation and maintenance of students-relationships affect the teaching learning process.

the study can be conducted across subject matter, grade levels, and instructional setting such as the college classroom and the corporate training room.

Therefore, instructional communication study should be continued and developed by the scholars. This current study focuses in exploring instructional strategies applied by the lecturers in EFL teaching. It is because, the successful of language learning depends on many aspects, one of them is communication. Additionally, teaching is as a communication process and participation is a form of communication and it serves a purpose. As the communicator in the class, the lecturer has the responsibilities to teach, guide, motivate, facilitate and mould learners to become useful and competent persons. Learners, on the other hand should absorb, seek and apply skill and knowledge shared in the classroom or other learning activities.

RESEARCH METDHOLOGY

This study used qualitative method with a case study. It was conducted at the campus of state and private universities in South Sulawesi, namely State University of Makassar and Muhammadiyah University of Makassar. The participants consisted of non-native English lecturers teaching in psycholinguistics, cross-culture understanding, translation, phonetics and phonology, and speaking class. This study did not focused on specific subject course, because it only investigated communication that occurred in the classroom. There were six lecturers involved in this research from two different universities, they were selected based on gender, age, and teaching experiences.

In collecting the data, the researcher used filed note in observation. The research focus was noted and recorded by handy camera. The observation was conducted for four times to each campus. The data in recording was transcribed into written form to be analyzed and interpreted. The data were analyzed qualitatively from Creswell (2014). Making an interpretation of the findings. The researcher related and compared the findings with information gleaned from the literature or theories, form interpretations that call for action agendas for reform and change. The researcher also discussed the literature at the end of the study. In interpretation, it also involves Discourse Analysis approach collaboratively to present the data in extract form.

FINDINGS

a. Beginning Strategies

Table 1: Beginning Strategies

Lecturer	Strategies
Lecturer 1	Giving quiz, showing the question on slide, dividing the questions into two types, calling the students by list number
Lecturer 2	Saying greetings, checking group preparation before presenting, watching the group presentation and taking some notes.
Lecturer 3	Asking the students’ condition, asking the students for standing up and dividing them into two large group

Lecturer 4	Introducing lesson topics in brief, standing position, speak loudly
Lecturer 5	Giving warming up activities, telling the lesson topics clearly and loudly, checking students preparation, making a joke before starting the lesson
Lecturer 6	Giving introduction of the course, grouping the students, asking the students to sit in the group

The table above indicates that most of the lecturers gave introduction and greeted before starting the lesson. Organizing the students to sit in group is also conducted in beginning of the class. Besides, warming up is also regarded as best strategies before explaining the materials. The form of warming up activities given are quiz and refresh the students’ body and mind. Telling the student for quiz in the next meeting let them to prepare their answer. The function of quiz is to ensure that all students are actively thinking. Moreover, starting the class by doing some joke is applied by some lecturers. It is effective to take the students’ mood for studying and make them comfortable during the lesson.

b. Explaining Strategies

Table 2: Explaining Strategies

Lecturer	Strategies
Lecturer 1	Incorporating the explanation by using slide and white board, using loud and clear voice, supporting the certain explanation by gesturing, modeling, body movement, and inserting humor, keep smiling. Mixing and switching the language in some situations.
Lecturer 2	Giving additional explanation after group presentation, modelling the example, giving chance to the students to give idea, inserting humor, gesturing, and connecting the materials with the real experience.
Lecturer 3	Writing some related vocabularies in the white board, giving comments after students’ presentation, inviting the students to give additional answer, discussing the difficult materials together. Switching and mixing the explanation.
Lecturer 4	Explaining the materials after group presentation, focusing on the difficult topic, gesturing, using clear voice.
Lecturer 5	Distributing handout, full standing in the class, gesturing and using body movement to support the explanation, inserting humor, smiling, using mimicry to model the words/explanation, pointing the different students to give idea or answer, showing the example by relating to the real context, writing related words/sentences on the whiteboard, and engaging the pointed students to answer the question by approaching them.

Lecturer 6	Giving explanation after group presentation, mixing and switching the explanation, inserting humor, standing position in explaining, giving chance to the other students to give questions for unclear topics.
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Table 2 displays the various strategies used by the lecturers in explaining the teaching materials in EFL teaching class. The way of explaining could influence students’ participation in the class. The data in the table indicates that each lecturer has their own way to explain the materials. Lecturer 1 incorporating the explanation by using slide and white board, using loud and clear voice, supporting the certain explanation by gesturing, modeling, body movement, and inserting humor, keep smiling. Mixing and switching the language in some situations. Lecturer 2 did not explain the teaching materials at the beginning but give additional explanation after group presentation

c. Teaching-Learning Activity

Table 3: Teaching-Learning Activities

Lecturer	Strategies
Lecturer 1	Quiz, presentation, group work, individual work, discussion, repetition drill, mini project.
Lecturer 2	Simulation, Cross-culture show, group work, discussion, question-answer, quiz
Lecturer 3	Presentation, pair work, discussion, question-answer
Lecturer 4	Group work, discussion, presentation
Lecturer 5	Discussion, individual work, role play, presentation, question-answer
Lecturer 6	Group work, presentation, individual work, mini project

Table 3 indicates that there are similarities of teaching activity used by the lecturers in EFL class. The strategies are giving quiz, presentation, group work, individual work, discussion, repetition drill, mini project, simulation, cross-culture show, group work, question-answer, quiz, pair work, and role play. Most the lecturers applied presentation and group as their main activity in the classroom. however, the application of those strategies is quite difference in the class. It based on the characteristic of the students and topic of the lesson.

d. Getting Students’ Attention

Table 4: Getting Students’ Attention Strategies

Lecturer	Strategies
Lecturer 1	Saying “let’s”, “everybody”, “are you with me?” loudly
Lecturer 2	Saying “listen” loudly
Lecturer 3	Saying “hi” and rise the hand, call the student’s name

Lecturer 4	Saying “hi, hello”, quiz time
Lecturer 5	Saying “hello” for several times
Lecturer 6	Saying “hello”, tapping the table

Table 4 shows that lecturers’ strategies applied to get students’ attention in class. The lecturers task is also to create conducive class in learning process. This condition is main factor in order to engage the students understand course materials. Thus, taking students’ attention is another way to keep the student focus and make the class conducive. The strategies are applied only when the student make noisy or busy to chat with their friends. The strategies applied was *responder calls with hand signal*. Besides, these strategies are also applied to ensure the students focus on the lecturers’ explanation. The application of taking students’ attention were saying *hi, hello, listen, everybody, are you with me?*. These were mentioned for many times and loudly. Most of them said *hello/hi* in many situation in the classroom.

e. Seating Arrangement Strategies

Table 5: Seating Arrangement Strategies

Lecturer	Strategies
Lecturer 1	Asking students to sit in pair, individual work
Lecturer 2	Dividing the students into some groups, determining the total member for each group, giving options for group topics, giving time before presentation
Lecturer 3	Dividing the students into two large group, pair work, presentation
Lecturer 4	Group presentation and discussion, the lecturer as moderator
Lecturer 5	Individual work for discussing the topic, pair work for presentation
Lecturer 6	Asking the students to work in group, determining the topic for each group, giving time limitation for completing the group work, group presentation

Table 4.5 shows that arranging students seating in the large class is important. Most of the lecturers applied group in the class. The students were asked to sit in group to discuss topic given. The other seating arrangements are students were asked to sit in pair and two large group. It is found also some models of sitting arrangement such U-model, island model, and circle model. The variation seating helps the lecturers to control the students. The lecturers are easier to walk around and assist the students.

f. Technological Strategies

Table 6: Technological Strategies

Lecturer	Strategies
Lecturer 1	Slide presentation, LCD projector, animation, picture

Lecturer 2	Music, video, slide presentation, LCD Projector
Lecturer 3	Google translator, android handphone
Lecturer 4	Slide presentation, LCD projector, pictures, electronic books, internet
Lecturer 5	Slide presentation, LCD projector, pictures
Lecturer 6	Slide presentation, LCD projector, pictures, internet

Table 6 indicates that instructional materials should be supported by technology. This strategy is related with the previous strategies. In this case, after dividing the students into some groups, then let them discuss out of the class, the group present the result of discussion by using slide presentation. The same case, the lecturers also provided their teaching material in power point and showed to the students while explaining. The LCD projector assisted lecturer’ explanation and group presentation.

g. Closing Class Strategies

Table 7: Closing Class Strategies

Lecturer	Strategies
Lecturer 1	Giving feedback, review, conclusion, project
Lecturer 2	Reviewing the materials, giving questions to discuss, quiz, show the group score
Lecturer 3	Giving feedback, review
Lecturer 4	Giving question answer, review and assignment
Lecturer 5	Giving Feedback, review, conclusion
Lecturer 6	Reviewing, conclusion, mini project

Table 7 displays lecturers’ strategies to end the class. Those strategies are all ways used by the lecturers to keep the students focus. One of the strategies are feedback from the students. The lecturers deliver the material with various ways to engage the students’ interest, so the students will be enthusiastic and stimulated. Lecturer 1, 2,3, and 5 applied giving feedback before ending the class as the closing strategies. Teaching and learning process is effective because the students are active to give feedback. Reviewing the materials applied by all the lecturers. Only two lecturers applied mini project as the last activity. The students were told the instruction of the project in the end of class. Time allocation for finishing the project was delivered clearly.

CONCLUSIONS

There are many instructional strategies in EFL class found at higher education. Some engage students to be active participant and some do not. From the discussion above, it indicates that the lecturers applied a variety of strategies at the beginning to the end of the class. This finding leads the researcher to claim that the strategies applied by

the lecturers can be categorized as active instructional strategies and passive instructional strategies. The category is based on the students responds and their activity.

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